

Exploring the Experiences of Public School Teachers as Electoral Boards

Rico M. Aya-ay

Holy Cross of Davao College, Davao City, Philippines

Abstract

Teachers have unique experiences that shape their views on the democratic process, from teaching learners about the importance of suffrage as a citizen to serving as electoral board members on election day. However, when serving in the election, teachers as electoral board members face a variety of challenges before, during, and after the election. This research study describes the lived experiences of public school teachers as electoral boards. It utilized phenomenological Research design with 12 public school teachers as participants for in-depth interviews and focus-group discussions. They were selected through a purposive sampling technique. Furthermore, an interview guide was utilized and the data gathered were transcribed through thematic analysis. The results revealed that in the lived experiences of public school teachers as an electoral board emerged major themes: Rational, Norm-based, and Affective. Based on the result, professional development programs, integration into curriculum, support networks, flexibility in work arrangements, and promotion of civic engagements are recommended.

Keywords: *Public school teachers, Electoral board members, national election, poll workers, public service motivation theory.*

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Introduction

Elections are crucial in molding the future of society in today's political scene. Teachers, as defenders of democracy, are frequently involved in the electoral process. Teachers have unique experiences that impact their opinions of the democratic process, from educating learners about the significance of suffrage as citizens to acting as poll workers on election day.

In the United Kingdom and Mexico, it has been seen that poll workers who are working during the elections are receiving a low salary for their service. (Clark & James, 2021; Cantu & Ley, 2017). In the Philippines, teachers who served last May 2022 national elections experienced a drastic problem. The election took place throughout the school year, coinciding with many public schools' returns to face-to-face classes following two years of remote learning due to the COVID-19 pandemic (Gloria, 2022). In Mindanao, teachers who served during the May 2022 National Election were concerned for their safety when there were armed men who grabbed vote-counting machines (VCM's); this caused the suspension of the election at a precinct for many hours because of the commotion (Inquirer.net, 2022). According to Munzert et al. (2020), the threat of violence against poll workers during elections is a serious concern. The impact of fear of being attacked, and the violence may cause a huge effect on the lives of the electoral boards that may result in a failure of the electoral process.

This result adds stressful work for the teachers serving the election and puts a burden on them. Teachers risk their lives by being overworked and neglecting their own mental and physical health requirements to

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serve with the election (Jomoad et al., 2021). In this regard, several studies internationally have been conducted on the struggles and challenges faced by poll workers serving elections.

This study is focused on the experiences of the teachers as the electoral board who have been serving the electoral process in the Philippines, as I have seen limited sources that focus on the experiences that teachers are facing serving the elections, especially in Davao City. The dissemination and publication of this study could be a great advantage to add as a source to the body of knowledge in the Philippines and internationally. This will also serve as a guide for future researchers as part of their literature review and studies.

This study is seen through the lens of the Public Service Motivation Theory Proposed by Perry and Wise (1990). Public service motivation (PSM) is described as an individual's tendency to respond to motives grounded primarily or exclusively in public institutions (Perry & Wise, 1990). This theory for public service motivation and identifies a typology of motives associated with public service that includes rational, norm-based, and affective motives. Three propositions are put forward that describe the behavioral implications of public service motivation.

Materials and Methods

Phenomenology is a qualitative research approach situated within the interpretivist research paradigm that seeks to understand the essence of individuals' lived experiences. This method focuses on how participants perceive and make meaning of a phenomenon, relying on rich descriptions provided by those who have directly experienced it (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Phenomenological research study method was used in this study allowed for the spontaneous emergence of the rich anecdotes and experiences of teachers who act as Electoral Boards during elections. The researcher worked hard to obtain the depths of experiences to be aware and educated about the common human experiences in the phenomena of teachers as electoral boards.

For the in-depth interview the participants of the study were six (6) teachers who served as an electoral board. For the focus group discussion, the participants of the study were six (6) teachers who served as an electoral board. They were chosen through a purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a type of non-probability sampling in which researchers choose participants of the population to participate in surveys depending on their own judgment (Alchemer, 2021). To be selected as a participant in the study, teachers must be presently teaching in the Schools Division of Davao. Teachers must also have served the election twice (2), whether in the national or local election in Davao City precincts.

This study used a semi-structured questionnaire, which is a sort of survey instrument used to collect data from study participants. It includes open-ended and closed-ended questions, some needing a precise response and others allowing for more thorough and individualized answers. The interview guide were created by the researcher. The interview guide included questions that was designed to elicit the experiences, coping strategies, and perspectives of the public school teachers serving on the electoral board. Moreover, probing questions was provided and validated by a panel of experts to be used for both the in-depth interview and focus-group discussion, which was delivered via a recorded face-to-face interview.

The researcher followed a systematic and time-efficient data-gathering procedure by first securing approval and obtaining REC certification, followed by permission from the DepEd Schools Division Superintendent and school principals. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before scheduling face-to-face interviews and focus group discussions. Data collection was conducted during onsite school duty while strictly following COVID-19 health protocols such as handwashing, wearing masks and face shields, social distancing, and vaccination verification. One-on-one interviews and FGDs were held in designated rooms to ensure safety and privacy. All collected data were organized and prepared for thematic analysis.

This research utilized thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is a method for analyzing qualitative data such as interviews, focus groups, and open-ended survey results. It entails detecting and interpreting data patterns, themes, and meanings (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Braun and Clarke highlighted the significance of remaining open-minded and reflective during the analytical process, as well as participating in a continual comparison process to verify that themes are grounded in data. Data will be arranged categorically based on the attributes and properties of a thing or a phenomenon.

Additionally, the researcher was able to triangulate their findings by doing focus group discussions. Triangulation is a research approach that includes gathering and analyzing data from many sources or methodologies in order to improve the validity and dependability of conclusions. It entails comparing and contrasting data from many sources or utilizing several approaches to collect data on the same issue. Hughes et. Al., (2017), defined triangulation as "cross-checking" data from several sources in order to boost the credibility of conclusions.

Adhering to ethical standards in research is essential for several reasons. Ethical norms support the pursuit of knowledge and truth while preventing errors and misconduct. For instance, prohibitions against fabricating, falsifying, or misrepresenting data help maintain research integrity and accuracy. This study complied with the guidelines set forth in Department of Science and Technology (DOST) Special Order No. 091, series of 2006, which emphasizes the protection of research participants from potential harm. These guidelines also reinforce the ethical framework and principles upheld by the Research Ethics Committee by the affiliate institution. To ensure participant safety and ethical integrity, the researcher strictly observed and documented all nine components of ethical considerations throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the data analysis. Discussions are included to offer a thorough understanding of the concepts. Refer to the quoted interview replies from the participants, both in IDI and FGD interviews.

Table 1. Experiences of Public School Teachers as Electoral Board

Main Themes	Sub-themes
Maximizing Tolerance	Applying Interpersonal Skills
	Fostering Inclusivity
Realizing Civic Fulfillment	Reflecting on Civic Duty
	Managing Time Constraints
Dealing with Operational and Psychological Barriers	Facing Operational Obstacles
	Going through with Emotional Stress
	Performing Non-Teaching Related Responsibilities

Maximizing Tolerance

The first category of the experiences of the Public School Teachers as Electoral Board is Applying Interpersonal Skills and Fostering Inclusivity. Teachers were inspired to engage in the election process because it allowed them to gain new skills and likely boosted their abilities as public servants and teachers. It also provides them the Pride and honor to be part of the electoral process, serving a transparent and honest election.

Applying Interpersonal Skills

The participant highlighted the need for good communication, emphasizing the value of explaining things in a pleasant manner since unpleasant conduct might reflect adversely on one's function as a teacher. Being an Electoral Board serves a crucial role for the Teachers as it also reflects their job as a teacher who manages the election as Electoral Boards. Teachers play a big role in properly communicating with

voters about the right thing to do during the election. Explaining them properly in a positive attitude towards the voters. Participant 5 shared:

"Eh explain lang sa ila in a nice way. kay lisud pud kaayo na kung ikaw bulyawan nimo sila niya teacher ka niya mabalik ra gihapon sa imoha. So ano jud siya big task jud siya, big responsibility." (You need to explain it to them in a nice way, because it would be difficult for you if you will shout to them wildly and you're a teacher it would also reflect to you as a teacher. So, that's it it's a big task and big responsibility for you). IDI, P5, L905-906.

Participant 5 stressed the importance of portraying the role of being a teacher inside the polling precinct as it would reflect your attitude. According to the article of Indeed (2023), People with high interpersonal skills are more likely to form positive relationships and collaborate well with others. They have a good understanding of people. People who have high interpersonal skills are typically preferred to work with. Moreover, during elections, teachers should always have a positive attitude and develop good interpersonal relationships with the voters to create a safe space for the voters, not only for them but also for the electoral board to have a smooth election process. In a similar way, the Participant shared the same experiences:

"Be patient siguro ka sa mga botante, for example highblood kayka suko na kaayo ko kapoy na kaayo ka dapat dili jud ko ipafeel sa ilaha or ipakita sa ilaha na nasuko ka kay basin awayon ka kana so dapat kanang patient jud nimo is taas jud sa ilaha dili pud pwde mag inistrikta kung ikaw na assign dinha kay basin awayon pud ka sa gubot na noon kalma jud ka patient niya mu-understand pud ka ilang mga quiries imo jud tubagon kay basin para malayo sa gubot". (Be patient with the voters. For example, if you're feeling frustrated and exhausted you should not show your irritation to them or let them see that you're upset, as it might lead to conflicts. You need to be patient with them and not act strictly if you're assigned there, as you might get involved in a dispute. Stay calm, be patient, and try to understand their queries and respond to them politely to avoid any trouble). FGD, P9, L1646-1652.

The Participant mentioned that they should always be composed and patient to any circumstances that may arise. Teachers who serve on electoral boards during elections might contribute essential skills to the process. Patience and composure are two important characteristics that may make a huge difference in ensuring a smooth and fair election process. Teachers may be patient while dealing with a varied range of voters, especially those unfamiliar with the voting process or having questions. Teachers are the ones who help voters comprehend the processes by providing instruction in a peaceful and at ease manner. Unexpected challenges or confusion may occur during election season. Teachers should always be calm and level-headed while dealing with these situations. Electoral Board 3 states that they should not give the voters the impression that they are upset or have a bad aura but rather be calm, patient, and composed with all of the voters' concerns.

The ability of a teacher to remain calm and manage their own stress in the midst of the problems that come with teaching. Teachers are less reactive as a result, and they are better equipped to help pupils with their own emotion management (Whitehead, 2022). In addition, being composed is needed during the elections, especially for the rude voter. According to Sevillano (2022), remaining calm in keeping an eye on the ballots while completing the processes and regulations to protect the validity of the votes. Teachers' patience and calm can help the election process go smoothly and honestly. Their experience working with various groups of people and their commitment to justice and accuracy allow them to serve on electoral boards during elections.

On the other hand, being initiative is also one of the skills that teachers acquired that helped them in day-to-day life especially during elections. They have cited that having initiative can proactively address any challenges or issues that may arise during election. Participant 6 cited:

"kuan kay ta initiative, kana initiative gyud dapat naa gyud initiative kay ngano madugay gyud ka, ma forty eight years gyud ka dili ka ma kuan. and then resourceful pud ka usabay ana, niya kuan pud unsa pamay mga unsa dira?. Mao lang to murag ing-ana". (When it comes to initiative, one really needs to have initiative because why would it take so long? If you've been around for forty-eight years and you still haven't

figured it out Also, you need to be resourceful at times. And, you know, what are the things there? That's just how it is, something like that.). IDI, P6, L1274 - 1277

Participant 6 highlights the importance of having initiative and being resourceful as teachers who serve the election. The participant is expressing that teachers as electoral board to be more proactive and resourceful, given the extended period of time they have been in their position. Additionally, Participant 6 also cited the same experience that their experience as electoral board allows them to acquire skills that are helpful for them. Participant 5 shares that:

"Being resilient, being patient and being abm determined and kana bitawng abm basin pa unsa pa imobang gi agian na hardships, kanang positive lang jud ka". (Being resilient, being patient, and being, um determined, and you know, whatever challenges you may face, just stay positive). IDI, P5, L990-992

Participant 5 emphasized the need to maintain resilience and optimism. Taking on obstacles enables them to develop vital abilities like patience, resilience, and optimism. Not only are these attributes useful for resolving issues, but they are also enduring characteristics that will support their development and enable them to face life's ups and downs with a calming attitude. The FGD participant also attested:

"Diskarte, naa man usabay sa handbook nga pwde ra man nimo dili ifollow nimo siya asa mas dali." (Strategy, sometimes it's in the handbook that you choose not to follow it for you your convenience, as it might be easier). FGD, P10, L1901- 1903

Participants share their experiences with initiative as they have learned what works better and faster for them to work with. They get this skill, which will be useful to them. Teachers who serve as electoral board taking initiative during the elections, this are vital in ensuring a fair and smooth elections.

Acquiring interpersonal skills is critical for teachers participating on election committees because it ensures successful collaboration as well as communication. These abilities helped teachers to collaborate effectively, make strong choices, and address difficulties that may emerge during the elections. Furthermore, strong interpersonal abilities help to the development of trust and credibility within the school community, producing an environment that's favorable to fair and transparent elections. The ability of teachers as members of the electoral board to work together improves the overall success and integrity of the election process.

The researcher believes that the election has a positive impact as well to the teachers, such as gaining a skill that will help teachers in their duty as electoral board and as a teacher. Their experiences reflect positive changes in society as they uphold big responsibilities in making sure that elections are fair and transparent. Thus, those experiences will help us determine how valuable their duties are, especially acquiring skills that will be beneficial to their profession as teachers.

Fostering Inclusivity

Teachers who serve on electoral boards promote diversity in the voting process. This might include guiding voter to the challenges faced and successful techniques used by teachers to increase inclusiveness and tolerance on electoral boards. This might include examining how they oversee divergent points of view, address potential biases, and guiding those who are not able to write and read in promoting productive discourse among a variety of people. In a statement of Participant 1 mentioned:

*"Sa far flung are usually gud ang mga tao kay mga lumad sila no kanang mostly sa ilaha kay hamtong na dili kabalo musulat ang ila lang jud tun-an nga pangalan ana kay ***** or ***** mao ra jud na kay mano mano ra man jud akong naabtan sa bukid (Barangay Elections), Moad ra jud na lisod siya kay kanang murag nay hawod hawod sa ilaha nga lumad maoy musulat pero ang masulat ra lagi ***** mao na jud"* (People in far-flung areas they are indigenous and mostly are old, they don't know how to write. They just only knew specific name of a politician, especially during manual elections (Barangay elections). That's the hard part there is someone who knows how to write in their community but the same thing a specific name of a politician). IDI, P1, L24-29

Participant 1 mentioned the reality of life in far-flung areas where only a few indigenous people are literate. This people lack literacy skills, especially in writing names of the politicians during barangay elections. The difficulty arises from the fact that only few of them only among the Indigenous People are literate, some of them are able to write but it is limited to a certain individual only. This was also attested in a FGD by one of the Participant, Participant 9 mentioned:

“So during sa election ang among na encounter didtoa kay more on ang mga tao didtoa is dili kabalo musulat dili kabalo mubasa madugay ang election because kay iguide jud nimo sila” (So, during election what we encountered there is mostly about the people who don’t know how to write and read. The election takes a long time because you really have to guide them.) FGD, P9, L 1356 – 1358

Participant 9 shares that during elections they observed that the majority of individuals lack literacy abilities having difficulty reading and writing. This difficulty tends to extend the election process since they must guide them through the process. The situation emphasizes the significance of resolving literacy challenges in order to streamline the voting process most especially in a far-flung area. Promoting fairness and transparency during elections is important as they portray their role being a teacher as well, this was attested by Participant 5:

“dili ka mag entertain og kanang something na kaila nimo na kanang unsa gani tawag ani?.. kaila nimo na mudagan na politiko or something eb ano nimo eb promote kay syempre ano baya ka teacher baya ka so dapat non-partisan, So dapat, kung бага fair ka ba and then fair pud ka sa uban pud na kuan. Dili kay purket naa kay kaila maoy paunabon. So first come first serve and of course diba naa man to mga priority lanes sa kanang buntis og sa mga senior, So dapat kuan jud ka just and fair pud ka when you are serving the ano during the election” (Do not entertain something that you are not familiar with, if you know someone who is running for a political position or something, you shouldn’t promote them because, of course, you are a teacher, so you should be a non-partisan. You should be fair, in a way, and fair to others as well. Just, because you know someone doesn’t mean they should be prioritized. So, it should be first come, first serve basis. There are priority lanes for pregnant women and seniors. So, you should really be just fair when serving the election). IDI, P5, L 816-824

Participant 5 highlights that it is crucial not to entertain personal ties while dealing with issues such as endorsing political figures, especially as a teacher who must stay non-partisan. Fairness is essential, and everyone should be treated equally, regardless of personal connection. Prioritizing services based on need, such as pregnant women and elders, corresponds with the concepts of justices and fairness in the electoral process. Participant 3 also mentioned the importance of playing neutral in any circumstances during election as it also reflects their role as a teacher in the classroom. Participant 3 shared:

“You do not play kanang abh...kanang favoritism. You stay in the middle you should be always neutral, kay specially during sa election kay makita ka nila pwede na siya ground for. So in other words sa teaching pud ingon ana pud. You should be neutral and you do not play favoritism in the class” (You should not engage in favoritism. You stay in the middle, you should always be neutral, especially during elections. Because they might see you as a potential ground for bias. So, in other words, the same goes for teaching you should be neutral and you should not play favoritism in the class). IDI, P3, L 548-551

Participant 3 highlights that maintaining neutrality and avoiding biases is vital, especially for teachers. To avoid any sense of bias, it is essential to strive to compromise and fairness, especially during sensitive times like elections. Maintaining fairness and impartiality in both teaching and election settings develops an atmosphere of confidence and assures equitable treatment. Furthermore, setting up priority lanes for pregnant women, who have illness and senior citizen is important to guide them for faster suffrage. They cited:

“imong bit bit bitbiton lang ato is maggyod ka atong mga naay mga sakit sakit naay sakit naay buntis mag uban sa ilaha imoha jud silang iguide ug tarong apil senior” (Guide and support those who have illnesses, those who are sick, and, pregnant women; accompany them and guide them properly, including the seniors.). FGD, P10, L 1506 – 1509

Participant 10 cited that the priority lanes ensure that the voters facing those physical challenges receive the necessary assistance and guidance from the electoral board during the election time, facilitating a smoother and more inclusive electoral process for the voters who have those conditions. Those considerations demonstrate a commitment equality in civic participations.

Fostering inclusion is critical for an electoral board member, according to the Public Service Motivation theory. Prioritizing equitable access to the political process, regardless of background or ability, contributes to the values of fairness and justice. This commitment to inclusion not only supports democratic norms, but it also corresponds with the intrinsic public service drive, which emphasizes the need of serving the whole community impartially.

The researcher believes that fostering inclusivity plays a vital role in implementing the basic policy of the commission of elections to maintain peace and order of the elections, especially in playing the integrity of the elections. Thus, this will also create a more dynamic and peaceful electoral process.

Realizing Civic Fulfillment

The second category of the experiences of the Public School Teachers as Electoral Board is "Realizing Civic Fulfillment." Teachers who serve on electoral boards reflecting on their responsibilities and roles as a teacher and as a citizen.

Reflecting on Civic Duty

Teachers' involvement is crucial in upholding the civic duty to ensure fair and transparent elections. Reflecting their commitment to the democratic process and their dedication to serving their communities. Despite the exhaustion, the participant considers the experience valuable, stressing the enjoyment they receive in addition to service credits. The participant was proud and appreciated the tremendous obligations bestowed upon them, underlining the government's trust and respect. Participant 1 clearly stated:

"Ako no I feel proud and at the same time nob kanang muana gyud ko kuyawa gyud ni teacher nob. kay kanang among the others ikaw man gud ang gitagaan og task kamoy gitagaan og responsibilities the big responsibilities diba?" (Me, I feel proud and at the same time, when I step up as a teacher, it's really challenging, right? Because among others, you're the one given the tasks, and you're given big responsibilities, isn't it?) IDI, P1, L180-183

Participant 1 felt proud of being a teacher. Teachers recognize the importance of democracy in society. Serving on an electoral board allows individuals to actively engage in defending democratic norms and guaranteeing fair elections, which is a source of pride for them. Teachers were permitted to participate actively in the election process like other professions. It also mentioned during the interview That Participant 3 felt proud being a teacher and being part of the election:

"Ah. Proud me kay. Number one abhh.... the right of suffrage na gihatag sa Filipino people. Teacher gyud ang mag process. So dako ang trust sa government og sa people sa teachers. So that's why we have to maintain that image nob nga murag ang trust na gihatag sa amoa sa mga Filipino, dako kaayo." (Ah. Proud of me. Number one, the right of suffrage given to the Filipino people. It's the teachers who process it. There's a great trust in the government and in the people in the teachers. So that's why we have to maintain that image, you know, the trust given us by the Filipinos, it's very significant.). IDI, P3, L474-478

The Participant expresses joy in being a part if the process of promoting the Filipino people's rights to suffrage. They highlight the vital function of teachers in this process, emphasizing the great level of trust placed in them by both the government and the people. The participant emphasizes the need of keeping a favorable image in order to sustain the Filipino people's faith in teachers. This indicates an awareness of teacher's duty and impact in establishing a trustworthy and successful election. The FGD participant also expresses their sentiment about this and they cited:

"Ang ako kay kanang makaproud man siya no kay kanang.. kanang part ta sa history na maka elect tag president kanang part ta sa process ba dili jud kanang mga doctor ilang gikuha ana teacher jud (What makes me proud,

is that you know, that part where we are part of the history where we can elect a president. That part of the process, they really choose teachers and not the doctors). FGD, P8, L1586 -1589.

Teachers tend to be well-educated individuals with experience comprehending and implementing processes. They are used to following rules and ensuring that processes are completed correctly. They were given the big responsibility of managing the election by the government as the people have given them respect and trust to uphold their integrity as a teacher and as an electoral board. Serving on the electoral board allows them to set a good example and highlight the value of civic engagement to their learners, demonstrating that active involvement in the political process is a vital duty. Participant 5 also mentions:

"So kung бага eh relate nako its not only serving sa election, abm ano towards your community towards sa imohang gina deal nimo na mga bata." (So, in a way, I can relate. It's not only about serving during the election but also about your contribution to community and the learners you deal with). IDI, P5, L980-981

The participant believes that participating in the election involves more than simply the act itself but also how they interact with their community and students. By serving on an electoral board, teachers provide a good example for their students and illustrate the importance of actively engaging in the political process. Serving on an electoral board is also a kind of community service. Teachers take satisfaction in giving back to their communities and serving as public servants in the government.

"Kuan kanang feelling fulfilled ka kay kuan na kay ambag ba pilay ambag dire bahahaah naa kay ambag ban aa kay ambag sa kuan sa kanang pagbabago sa atoang kuan sa country?" (When you feel fulfilled because, you know, you have contributions, Do you have a contribution there, do you have a contribution in, you know, the changes in our country). FGD, P12, L 1621-1623

The participant expressed a sense of fulfillment gained from making a contribution, highlighting the recognition of their significance. The "ambag" or contribution in English implies a personal involvement in bringing about change in our society. This demonstrates a favorable attitude toward the concept with their efforts adding up to the larger societal change.

According to Gloria (2022), pride is one of the most important motivations for teachers volunteering. Teachers are viewed as trustworthy and reliable members of society, which boosts faith in the democratic process. Teachers who serve on electoral boards have many reasons to be proud of their position. Their contributions to the democratic process, adherence to fairness and integrity, and dedication to community service make their participation vital and beneficial. It expresses a sense of civic responsibility and dedication to the democratic principle. Additionally, for teachers who volunteer, pride is a motivating factor that is very important because it is their reputation as dependable and trustworthy members of society, which not only makes them feel good about themselves but also helps people believe more in the democratic process because of their hard work (Bautista, 2023).

The researcher believes that teachers demonstrate a dedication to their community and the political process. A key component of civic duty is their involvement in guaranteeing fair and transparent elections. Their participation as electoral board emphasizes the importance of teachers as vital contributors to the nation's electoral process.

Managing Time Constraints

The participants underlined the importance of teaching first since it is critical for the learner's development. They emphasized the significance of spending sufficient time to their responsibilities as the electoral board. Recognizing the importance of time management in becoming a well-rounded teacher and guaranteeing a successful and fair election process. Here are some of the experiences of the participants:

"Abm. maybe siguro in preparing, so of course ang pinaka first jud na kuan no, abm task jud dira sa teacher kay, kani man jud ang among first jud na ano nob na job, then kani siya is secondary nalang man ni ang kuan. Ang priority jud magtudlo sa jud ko sa mga bata. kung time sa klase time sa jud sa klase. niya kung naa nay kuan

kung after classes na so diba na ang time na mag prepare ka na mag attend ka og orientations about sa ano sa activity during sa elections.” (Maybe in preparing, so of course the very first thing is, the primary task for a teacher is teaching. That’s our first job, and this electoral duty comes secondary. Teaching the children is the priority, it its class time, its class time. And if there are any electoral duties, they are scheduled after classes, and that’s when you prepare and attend orientations about election activities.) IDI, P5, L886-889

It reveals how the teachers manage their time; the most important thing is to balance everything, prioritizing the task as a teacher preparing lessons ahead of time, preparing for the grades, and allocating time for the preparations of the elections. Preparations are vital for the smooth flow of the elections. Participants also shares about their valuable experience as to how they manage their time:

”Ahm. Balance. Yun, yun like what I said kanina, prioritizing eh balance nimo. Ah as a teacher you prioritize first your first task as a teacher. That’s why like what I said kanina, compute your grades first, then of course you did your, you made your lesson plans for the rest of the week.” (Ah, balance. Like what I mentioned earlier, its about prioritizing. As a teacher, you prioritize your primary role as a teacher. That’s why, as I mentioned earlier, you calculate your students grades first, and then, of course, you create your lesson plans for the rest of the week) IDI, P4, L682-685

Participant 4 expresses that planning ahead of time is important so they can focus their time on their job as an electoral board. Planning is crucial, especially for the teachers, computing the grades ahead of time and planning the lessons and other school tasks that they need to comply. It also allows them to operate the election smoothly as they plan their tasks as an electoral board. During election period teachers who are electoral board will not have a hard time doing their tasks as they had already planned their work ahead of time. Participant 5 also shares their experiences as to how they handle situations during the election, especially time management:

”So, dili man jud siya ma hilabtan or dili siya ma distract ang klase kay ang pagkuha sa mga paraphernalia is during saturday, sunday ana. and then ab sa time pud sa election butdon ko man jud na tanan. na walay klase ana kay magsulod man jud ko og kining kuan. So ano lang proper time management ing-ana kay lisud pud kaayo nob na mapabayaan nimo ang imong klase.” (So, the class won’t be affected or distracted because the preparation of election materials is done on Saturdays and Sundays. Also, during the election day, I take the whole day off, so there are no classes. I go into this role. So it’s just proper time management like that, because it’s really challenging to neglect your class) IDI, P5, L 877-883

It is evident that Participant 5, focused on teaching assignments before attending to their electoral board responsibilities. They feel that if they do these teaching duties perfectly, they will be able to focus on the electoral board duties. This way, they can do their best as an electoral board member which is responsible to have an honest and transparent election. Additionally, Participants from FGD attested and experience the same scenario, citing:

”Ang DEPED man gud mubatag man gud sila pila ka adlaw nga walay klase, dili jud madistorbo.” (DepEd really gives a certain number of days without classes, and they really shouldn’t be disturbed) FGD , P12, L1782-1783

The participant mentions that the DepEd is thoughtful by allocating several days off from classes, ensuring that the regular academic schedule is not disrupted. This proactive approach indicates DepEd’s dedication in maintaining time management among teachers as electoral boards. This allows teachers to prepare efficiently with their duties as teacher and at the same time being an electoral board serving the election. Additionally, participant from FGD as well mentions the same experience with this, having importance on time management:

”Maghatag man pud ug ample time ang COMELEC nga makaprepare ka makafocus ka sa imong pagserve ug kanang makabuhat ka daan sa imong trababoon as teacher kay pressure mana diba lang man ka mangkuan ug resume na ug human election.” (COMELEC also provides ample time for you to prepare and focus on your service, so that you can already accomplish your tasks as a teacher, because there’s pressure when you’re just asked for you to resume after the election) FG, P12, L1763-1767

The participant mentions that COMELEC takes an organized strategy by allowing teachers sufficient time to prepare and focus on their jobs as election servers. This proactive technique enables teachers to do extensive preparation, preparing ahead of time for their duty as a teacher and after being an electoral board. Understanding their roles aims to alleviate difficulties associated with their job.

According to Coguric (2023), Good time management may help people create trust and confidence. This may demonstrate their dependability and professionalism. It can help people avoid feeling overwhelmed and frustrated. It can deal with stress and uncertainty while also preventing weariness and exhaustion. When done correctly, people may minimize stress, avoid the rush, and be delighted with the result – it's a win-win situation. Teachers can successfully balance their roles as electoral board members by using efficient time management. This not only helps to ensure a fair and transparent election, but it also supports their educational purpose. In summary, time management is a key ability that assists individuals in making the best use of their time, achieving their objectives, reducing stress, and living more balanced and productive lives (Baustista, 2023).

The researchers believes that the participants attention on prioritizing time management, and the strategic allocation of particular hours for electoral obligations demonstrates a proactive and structured approach to balancing teaching and political responsibilities. The inclusion of vacations as an ideal period for election activity corresponds to a practical schedule factor. These observations demonstrate an intelligent approach, demonstrating the participants dedication to properly manage the demands of both tasks.

Dealing with Operational and Psychological Barriers

The third category of the experiences of the Public School Teachers as Electoral Board is "Dealing with Operational and Psychological Barriers." Teachers who serve on electoral boards may face practical and psychological challenges. Addressing these obstacles is critical to ensuring they can carry out all their duties smoothly.

Facing Operational Obstacles

The participant was frustrated by the lack of an established system during election time. Teachers were totally disappointed with the struggles that they encountered during and after the election. These struggles may affect the teachers giving them stress, anxiety, fear, etc. One of those is the lack of a clear system for queuing upon transmitting the ballot boxes in the Comelec Office and Sanggunian Building. This is one problem that teachers are facing long ques that can causes stress among teachers. Here are excerpts of their interview responses:

"ahh.... ay oh kana lang ang problema lang nako kay katong pag kining mag kanang pila gani na walay klaro syempre daghan jud kaayo og kanang murmur ing-ana kung pwede lang unta nga naay kanang kining tama na proseso murag tama na tanan ano gani system na para dili na mag duot." (Ahh.. yes, my only problem is that when there's a lack of clarity when it comes to the people, of course, there's a lot of murmuring going on. It would be a great if there's a proper process or system in place to avoid such confusion).
IDI, P5, L835-839

Participant 5 expresses concern over a lack of clarity in some instances, notably when dealing with a bunch of crowd, which results in widespread confusion and complaining. The need for a clear and proper procedure or system indicates a desire for efficiency and transparency, stressing the difficulties that occur in the absence of such system. This realization emphasizes the importance of well-defined system for fostering order and reducing confusion. This was also attested by participant 6 as they cited:

"mura siya og pinatyanay ba kay ngano magka buang ka niya wala silay kanang, gamay man gud ang manpower sa comelec, So wala gani mo kuan gani sa imo mo assist na oh magpila, niya magpa-unhanay, niya usabay mawala na ang pagka maestra sa uban kay bisan nauna tong isa niya musingit nalang." (It's like they're pushing and pushing because why would you act so crazy when Comelec has limited manpower? So if they don't even ask you or guide you where to queue or how to line up, sometimes, the professionalism of other can disappear because even if someone was there ahead of time, they just insert in).
IDI, P6, L1033 – 1037

The struggles of the Teachers transmitting the ballot boxes in the Comelec site are the most crucial for the teachers. There is no clear system for transmitting the ballot boxes. There was chaos upon lining up; some of the teachers lining up inserted the line prior to the one at the first line, which caused chaos among teachers. Some of the teachers are traveling far to transmit the ballot boxes in the city. Participant also shares their experiences:

“after na sa election no ibatod na sa dire sa city kay dire na sa bukid. Anbi mi syudad gibatod na buntag na kapoy, mao lang man siya akong naexperience.” (After the election, it will be taken to the city because we’re here in the rural area, after that we will go home in the next morning, we’re tired and that’s the only experience I had). FGD, P11, L1408-1410

Participant mentions the struggle they had to transmit the ballot boxes from the rural areas to the city from lining up to transmit them. A lot of teachers are there transmitting the ballot boxes. They will be caught until the next morning. This is the main struggle of teachers, especially with the poor system of the government to the teachers upon transmitting the ballot boxes to the COMELEC sites, and they also lack personnel who will assist the teachers in submitting the ballot boxes. This struggle have been always the problem of teacher ever since that there was no concrete plan of action from the officials of COMELEC. Participant 2 expresses its experience, as they cited:

“ang pinaka ano nako is wala pajud na ano na resolve ang kana ganing mag submit og mga paraphernalia didto sa..sa gym, asa kaning sa.. unsa gani nang diha sa ano?... abbb Sanggunian niya pagkabuman sa Magsaysay na pinaka kapoy jud na siya wala pajud kay tungod sa kadaghan.” (My main concern is that the issue of submitting paraphernalia there in the... in the gym, where is that.... Sanggunian, after Magsaysay, it’s really exhausting because of the crowd). IDI, P2, L257-261

Participant 2 expresses dissatisfaction with the unsolved problem of submitting electoral paraphernalia in the COMELEC sites after the election. Participant 2 emphasizes the difficulty, attributing it to exhaustion to the part of the teachers during the return of materials and the amount of work they have portrayed during election. They are looking for a solution for this problem. Teachers was affected by this problem, they also cited their experience with the poor system of COMELEC pointed out the issue of having an incompetent third member from the COMELEC:

“Ang third member is gina fill inan nila ug sa COMELEC sir ang problema ang ginabatag man gud nila sir kay dili kaayo siya ingon na competent sir ba ang third member sir kay naa man gud na siyay bubaton sir, mag ingon mi bubaton ni nila dili man sila kabalo so as a poll clerk magdugay imong trabaho kailangan pa man nimo siya ignide wherein kung teacher na siya dali ra ka cope.” (They filled in the third member, and the problem is with the COMELEC. The issue there is that they gave him tasks, but they are not very competent, sir, because they has their own responsibilities. We say we’ll do something, but they dont know how, so as a poll clerk, your work takes longer because you still need to guide him. If it was a teacher, it would be easier for you to cope) FGD, P8, L1740-1745

The participants express the problem with the third member from the COMELEC who seems incapable, causing delays in the work and needing extra guidance. This issue is hindering progress and making the process more challenging. It highlights the importance of having competent and efficient team members to ensure smooth and timely completion of tasks, as sometimes COMELEC fills the Third member position to a civilian and not a Teacher, especially during barangay elections. With this, it caused delayed with their work as they have to handle and make sure that the civilian third member is doing right.

According to Chi (2023), future elections must include a "systematic retrieval of election paraphernalia" to prevent teachers and volunteer poll workers from putting themselves at risk in transporting election equipment. This is an evident situation of the teachers after the elections, the struggle of no clear system for the retrieval of election materials in the COMELEC Offices. Additionally, according to Cruz (2023), in order to reduce the risk to teachers and volunteer poll workers and ensure their safety, it is imperative that a "systematic retrieval of election paraphernalia" be implemented in future elections. This would relieve them of the burden of transporting election equipment.

The Lens of Public Service Motivation Theory was seen in this scenario that teachers, as they remain devoted to their work over time, face those problems especially the poor system returning the ballots and other paraphernalia. Despite the struggle that they had faced, they remain devoted, however they felt disappointed and unmotivated by the poor system. However, their dedication and commitment still overflows, and find purpose with their work.

Going through with Emotional Stress

Serving as an electoral board member can be emotionally draining. Teachers working in elections are vulnerable to stress as a result of the exhaustion they experience when serving in elections. It is also critical to understand that the electoral board is a difficult responsibility, and emotional stress is expected of the challenges involved. In one instance during the interview, the participants mentioned that they felt anxious and tired. This instance expresses the struggle that teachers faced during the election as electoral board. Participant 3 shared that:

"Kuan siya abhh. Kulba siya, kulba but, so far na.. ano lang man gibapon na solve man kay at first katong pag send namo wala na send ang amoang result. So naabtan mi gyud og alas dyes pagka following day pa, aya siya nasend ang among result. So murag kapoy siya. Mao nang naka ingon ko na dili nako mo serve basta ingon ani obob. Kay kapoy siya kaayo." (It's really nervous, very nervous, but so far, it got resolved. At first, when we sent our results, it didn't send. We had to wait until 10 o'clock the following day before our results were sent. So, it seemed exhausted. That's why I said I wouldn't serve if it's going to be like this because it's really exhausting). IDI, P3, L491-494

This apparent situation of Participant 3 expresses a strong feeling of worry as they cannot send the result to the server. It causes stress for the teachers as it may cause delays. Serving in an election often entails lengthy working hours that can continue into the dawn, during election day, and vote counting, which can add to the teacher's stress from their worn-out work. Moreover, amidst their struggle during the election process, teachers are still focused and maintain a positive outlook that the election will be finished successfully. The participant believes that stress mainly comes from doing something wrong or illegal, they cited:

"Kasi usually man gud ang makapa stress sa imo if ever naa kay gibubat na mali or naa kay illegal na gibubat. So naa kay gitaguan, naa kay secrets mao na siya ang number one na nakapa stress, siguro." (Usually, what causes stress is when you're doing something wrong or engaging in illegal activities. So, if you have something to hide, if you have secrets, that's the number one thing that causes stress, perhaps.) IDI, P4, L649-651

The participants believes that stress occurs mostly when they do something wrong or against the law. This implies that participants relates stress with the fear of making errors or indulging in behaviors that are prohibited. This is one of the factors that will lead teacher go through emotional stresses. Participants 6 also expresses the same scenario of their experience when they are stress, Participant 6 cited:

"Pag ma stress ko diba. Actually, dili nako na siya gina mind gina kuan nako siya na positive lang gyud diba? kay lalo na pag chairman ka ikaw man gud mag lead sa group." (When I get stressed, right? Actually, I don't let it bother me. I just focus on the positive, right? Especially when you're the chairman, you have to lead the group). IDI, P6, L 1132-1134

Participant 6 recognizes stress; they emphasize on making the deliberate decision not to focus on it. The participant develops a mentality aimed towards resilience and keeping a positive attitude by opting to concentrate on the good parts. By focusing emphasis on more positive viewpoints and coping mechanisms, this technique advocates taking proactive steps to alleviate their stress. The focus group discussion participant also agrees with the stresses that they have encountered; they have shared:

"kung naay mga struggle kung naay mga problema muchill ra jud ko kay kabalo man ko na akong mga kauban nga muback up mu support para masulbad." (when there are struggles or problems, I just stay clam because I know that my companions will back me up and support to find a solution). FGD, P12, L1668-1770

The Participant exhibits a resilient mindset in facing difficulties and challenges, saying that they do not let it go to them since they have their colleagues who will help them to figure things out. This realization emphasizes the need for teamwork and a supportive environment in conquering obstacles, stressing the power that comes from addressing problems as a group as opposed to doing it alone. Another experience of teachers was having fear of their safety that causes them to overthink about their safety. Participant 9 shares:

“hadlok lang jud siya kay ang naa didtoa kay mga NPA mga ing ana mao lang jud ang hadlok ba, niya ang Pulis kay lain sab ang paminaw nga naa ang pulis sa imong kuan. Pati pulis mabadlok kay wala sila kabalo ug tirabon sila. So after sa election hadlok gibapon siya kay mubyabe man ka sige kag bitbit ana layo pa siya na area muagi gud ka ug dalan ana na critical na dalan nga ngitngit kaayo ibyabe pa namo na ug gabie” (It is just really scared because the area there is occupied by NPA rebels, that’s the only fear we had. Even the police are afraid because they don’t know if they’ll be targeted. So even after the election, it is still scared because you have to travel carrying (ballot boxes), and we had to pass through a dark and critical road, which is very dim lit, especially if you have to travel at night” FDG, P9, L 1361-1366

Participant 9 expresses a sense of worry and concern caused by the presence of NPA insurgents in the area. Fear grips not only for the electoral board, but even to the police force, which is concerned about being targeted by the rebels while in their duty during election time. This causes fear and being anxiety of the teachers as electoral board while serving the elections.

According to Shain (2020), Having a positive outlook encourages one to keep trying rather than giving up. It enables us to keep our objectives and ambitions in mind so that we may act on the drive to continue working toward them. Moreover, teachers retain a positive attitude; working on an electoral board can be hard, but maintaining optimism and motivation that their work is rewarding and fulfilling. Their commitment to the democratic process and the idea that they are contributing to the greater good allows them to persevere and remain optimistic about the election's success. Teachers have a resilient optimistic attitude, handling the obstacles of serving on an electoral board with unshakable optimism and enthusiasm, inspired by the conviction that their efforts would be rewarded and fulfilled in the long run (Chi, 2023).

The researcher believes that the participants may experience stress and fatigue; they still adopted having that mindset of being resilient, believing that the challenging situation is just temporary and soon it will end. Additionally, they emphasized that maintaining a positive outlook, particularly leadership is an effective tool to manage their stress during the demanding situation of election.

Performing Non-Teaching Related Responsibilities

Recognizing the importance of their function as an electoral board member, the participant voluntarily and temporarily relinquishes their teaching obligations. By making this planned choice, they desire to dedicate their full attention and efforts to the complex and tough obligations related to their electoral board duties. This strategic move demonstrates their dedication to preserving the integrity of the election process, protecting individuals' right to vote freely and fairly, and contributing to the democratic framework's fundamental functioning. Putting aside their teaching duties for the duration of the election, the participants emphasize the severity and importance of their electoral board position, exhibiting a determined and unwavering dedication. Participant 6 shares its valuable insight:

“So pag electoral board ka or as BEI ka during the time ang akong mind set is electoral board ko. Ana so mao ni akong task karon. Anyways si, Set aside sa si teacher. Pero mugawas man gibapon ang pagka teacher nato oiy diba?” (So when you’re an electoral board member part of the BEI, my mindset is that I am an electoral board member. That’s my task for now. Anyway, we can set aside the fact that we’re teachers, but our role as teachers still comes out right?). IDI, P6, L1116-1168

This is a portrayal that teachers are exceptional, making things all possible, setting aside being a teacher while serving the election. However, that doesn't make sense as it mentions that they are natural teachers and will still come out being a teacher. Exhibiting their dual purpose being an electoral board, and at the same time, they were given the task by the government to be an electoral board. On the other hand, since

elections come on holidays, the participant finds it simpler to balance obligations, for instance, election briefings are held on Saturdays to prevent conflict with teaching obligations. Participants share their experiences :

"Abh. Kuan man time management and dili man siya mag clash ang time namo kay kung mag election man pud Holiday man siya, So dili man siya matunong og ano. Wala man siyay klase oh. So okay lang." (Ah, its about time management, and our time doesn't clash because during elections, it's a holiday. So it doesn't interfere with anything. We don't have classes, so its okay.). IDI, P3, L528-530

The participant stresses the value of time management. Participant mentions that since elections usually happens on a holiday, handling obligations is more convenient. This observation implies that the election schedules aligned with holidays offers that electoral board members useful benefit, enabling them to manage their responsibilities better. Participant 3 also pointed out the same experience:

"So far ang mga, okay lang kay abhh... ang mga, kanang mga seminars and kaning mga briefing ang comelec will fall on saturday naman. Unlike before na during school days. Karon they see to it na it will fall on saturdays para dili siya mag kuan sa official days sa mga teachers. "(So far, it's okay because, you know, the seminars and briefings from the COMELEC will fall on Saturdays. Unlike before when it used to be during school days. Now they make sure it's on Saturdays so it doesn't disrupt the teachers' official workdays) IDI, P3, L522-524

The participant appreciates that election briefings are being scheduled on Saturdays since it avoids difficulties with their teaching duties. This realization shows gratitude for the thorough planning that enables the participant to carry out their electoral duties and teaching obligations. Additionally, participant from FGD attested to the same scenario earlier about balancing time:

"tong briefing nila kay sabado man to so dili siya maka kuan sa aming class hours kay ginakuan nil ana Saturday so walay klase dili kaayo apektado ang klase." (Their briefing is on Saturday, so it doesn't interfere with our class hours because they schedule it on Saturday when there are no classes. Classes are not really affected) FGD, P8, L1784 - 1786

The participant, emphasizes the advantage of holding election briefing on Saturdays so as to avoid interfering with regular teaching times. The participant dedication to limiting the impact on their primary task of teaching is evident in this strategic planning, which also shows their awareness of their dual duties. From the FGD Participant as well it also stated the same experience citing:

"Maghatag man pud ug ample time ang COMELEC nga makaprepay ka makafocus ka sa imong pagserve ug kanang makabuhay ka daan sa imong trabahoon (COMELEC also provides ample time for you to prepare, focus on your service, and accomplish your tasks in advance):. FGD, P12, L1763-1766

It mentions the COMELEC provides enough time so that they can prepare and concentrate on their election serving duties. This emphasizes how crucial it is to provide everyone participating in political processes the time to prepare so they can fulfill their duties efficiently. The focus on early planning suggests a dedication to the efficient and well-coordinated completion of election-related duties. The COMELEC has taken a proactive stance in providing this preparatory time to make sure that teachers are prepared and able to carry out their responsibilities during elections.

Teachers' duty will not be compromised as they shifted to being an electoral board serving the election, as it was discussed that briefing, training and other matters should fall during weekends. Teachers may face situations in which their professional interests as educators clash with their jobs as impartial electoral board members, requiring them to strike a difficult balance between their devotion to education and the needs of impartiality in the electoral process. It is difficult to serve as an electoral board member and a teacher at the same time. Balancing many obligations might result in apparent or actual conflicts of interest. Teachers may face circumstances in which their professional interests as teachers clash with their jobs as impartial electoral board members. As a result, teachers are not only champions of education but also poll security agents. (Nicholls, 2022).

The Principal Agent Theory model has seen in this theme that it becomes imperative to provide clear communication, furnish sufficient resources, and institute accountability systems in order to align the concerns of both sides and preserve the credibility of the political procedure. The Principal-Agent Model sheds light on the dynamics and difficulties that arise. The Principal-Agent Model is exemplified by the delegation of responsibilities from the Commission on Elections (COMELEC) to teachers, emphasizing the critical reliance on teachers' integrity and competence for a fair electoral process, with transparent communication and accountability playing critical roles in navigating potential challenges.

Thus, teachers and the principal which is the COMELEC works hand in hand to provide excellent time management schemes so that it would manage well both the responsibilities of teachers being as well an electoral board without compromising their dual responsibilities. Can focus on each specific tasks on time.

Conclusion, Implications, and Future Directions

The results showed that teachers experienced both benefits and challenges before, during, and after elections, including skill development, civic fulfillment, financial incentives, and operational and psychological difficulties. Their role was found to be crucial in ensuring honest and transparent elections, and their experiences contributed to improved professionalism, resilience, and understanding of democratic processes. Using the Public Service Motivation Theory, the study revealed that teachers were more motivated by norm-based and affective factors (sense of duty and passion for service) rather than purely rational or monetary considerations. Future directions include professional development programs, integration of civic education in the curriculum, support networks, flexible work arrangements, promotion of civic engagement, and policy advocacy to support teachers' dual roles. These recommendations aim to strengthen the connection between education and democracy and contribute to quality education and participatory communities.

Overall, the study highlights that teachers' service as electoral board members not only strengthens democratic processes but also enhances their professional growth and civic responsibility, making their role essential in fostering both effective education and democratic participation.

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